

A study on continuous functions in semi prime ideal space

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Abstract: In this paper new type of continuous functions namely S-continuous introduced in semi prime ideal space and compare with continuous function in topological space and study some of their properties. Also we introduced strongly S-continuous and S-irresolute in semi prime ideal space and compared with S-continuous in semi prime ideal space. Totally S-continuous and contra S-continuous were introduced and discussed.

Key words: S-continuous, strongly S-continuous, totally S-continuous.

1. Introduction

Ideals in a topological space (X, τ) is treated in the classic text by Kuratowski [7]. An ideal I on a topological space (X, τ) is a non empty collection of subsets of X which satisfies (i) $A \in I$ and $B \subseteq A$ implies $B \in I$. (ii) $A \in I$ and $B \in I$ implies $A \cup B \in I$. A topological space together with an ideal I is called an ideal topological space and denoted by (X, τ, I) . He also defined the local function for each subset of X with respect to an ideal I and τ . Given a topological space (X, τ) with an ideal I on X and if $\rho(X)$ is the set of all subsets of X , a set operator $(.)^* : \rho(X) \rightarrow \rho(X)$ called a local function of A with respect to τ and I is defined as follows: For $A \subseteq X$, $A^*(I, \tau) = \{x \in X / U \cap A \notin I \text{ for every } U \in \tau(x)\}$ where $r(x) = \{U \in \tau / x \in U\}$. A kuratowski closure operator $(cl)^*(.)$ for a topology $\tau^*(I, \tau)$ called $*$ -topology finer than τ is defined by $(cl)^*(A) = A \cup A^*(I, \tau)$. We denote A^* for $A^*(I, \tau)$ and τ^* for $\tau^*(I, \tau)$. Further Vaidyanathaswamy [12] extended the study of ideals and local functions. The properties of the topology generated by the ideal I and τ , called the star topology which is finer than τ , denoted by τ^* are studied by Vaidyanathaswamy, Hashimoto, Hayashi and Samuels [4]. In 1990, Jankovic and Hamlet [3] in addition to their findings, consolidated all the results. A function $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is said to be continuous if inverse image of every open in Y is open in X . Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ be two bijection mappings. Then $g \circ f : Y \rightarrow Z$ is also bijection mapping and $(g \circ f)^{-1} = f^{-1} \circ g^{-1}$. In 2021 we introduced prime ideals in topological space and study some properties [10]. Also we introduced semi prime ideal space in a topological space [11]. In this research paper we introduced S-continuous, strongly S-continuous and S-irresolute in semi prime ideal space and discussed.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. A semi prime ideal S on a topological space (X, τ) is a nonempty collection of subsets of X which satisfies (i) $A \in S$ and $B \subseteq A$ implies $B \in S$. (ii) $A \cap B \in S$ and $A \in S$ implies $B \in S$. The space (X, τ, S) is said to be a semi prime ideal space.

Definition 2.2. Given a topological space (X, τ) with a semi prime ideal S on X and if $\rho(X)$ is the set of all subsets of X , a set operator $(.)_S^* : \rho(X) \rightarrow \rho(X)$ is called a semi prime local function of A with respect to τ and S is defined as follows: For $A \subseteq X$, $A_S^*(S, \tau) = \{x \in U / U \cap A \notin S \text{ for every } U \in r(x)\}$ where $r(x) = \{U \in \tau / x \in U\}$.

Definition 2.3. A subset A of a semi prime ideal space (X, τ, S) is said to be S -closed if $A_S^* \subseteq A$.

Definition 2.4. A subset A of a semi prime ideal space (X, τ, S) is S -open if its complement is S -closed.

Result 2.1. Every open is S -open.

Definition 2.5. A subset A of a semi prime ideal space is said to be S -clopen if it is both S -closed and S -open.

Definition 2.6. A function $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is said to be totally continuous if inverse image of every open in Y is clopen in X .

Definition 2.7. A function $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is said to be contra continuous if inverse image of every open in Y is closed in X .

Definition 2.8. Let (X, τ) be a topological space and let $x \in X$. Then the neighbourhood of x is an open set of X containing x .

3. Continuous functions in semi prime ideal space

In this section we defined S -continuous and discussed some properties.

Definition 3.1. A function $f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is said to be S -continuous if inverse image of every open in Y is S -open in X .

Example 3.1. Consider the semi prime ideal space

$X = \{a, b, c\}, \tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}, S = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}, \sigma = \{\phi, \{b\}, X\}$. Define $f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ by $f(a) = b, f(b) = c, f(c) = a$. Then f is S -continuous.

Definition 3.2. A function $f : (X, \tau, S_1) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S_2)$ is said to be S -irresolute if the inverse image of every S -open in Y is S -open in X .

Example 3.2. Consider the semi prime ideal spaces $X = \{a, b, c\},$

$\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, X\}, S = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}$ and

$Y = \{a, b, c\}, \sigma = \{\phi, \{b\}, X\}$. Define $f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S)$ by $f(a) = b, f(b) = c, f(c) = a$. Then f is S -irresolute.

Definition 3.3. A function $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S)$ is said to be strongly S -continuous if inverse image of every S -open in Y is open in X .

Example 3.3. Consider the semi prime ideal space $X = \{a, b, c\},$

$\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$, and $Y = \{a, b, c\},$

$\sigma = \{\phi, \{b\}, X\}, S = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}$. Define $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S)$ by $f(a) = b, f(b) = c, f(c) = a$. Then f is strongly S -continuous.

Theorem 3.1. *Every continuous is S-continuous.*

Proof. Let $f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a continuous function and let U be any open in Y . Since f is continuous, $f^{-1}(U)$ is open in X and hence $f^{-1}(U)$ is S -open in X . Therefore f is S -continuous. \square

Remark 3.1. *The converse of the above theorem need not be true as shown in the following example.*

Example 3.4. *Consider the semi prime ideal space $X = \{a, b, c\}$,*

$\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$, and $Y = \{a, b, c\}$,

$\sigma = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$, $S = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}$. Define $f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ by $f(a) = a, f(b) = b, f(c) = c$. Then f is S -continuous but not continuous..

Theorem 3.2. *Every strongly S-continuous is continuous.*

Proof. Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S)$ be strongly S -continuous and let U be any open set in Y . Since every open is S -open, U is S -open. Since f is strongly S -continuous, $f^{-1}(U)$ is open in X and hence f is continuous. \square

Remark 3.2. *The converse of the above theorem need not be true as shown in the following example.*

Example 3.5. *Consider the semi prime ideal space $X = \{a, b, c\}$,*

$\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$, and $Y = \{a, b, c\}$,

$\sigma = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$, $S = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}$. Define $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S)$ by $f(a) = a, f(b) = b, f(c) = c$. Then f is continuous but not strongly S -continuous.

Theorem 3.3. *Every strongly S-continuous is S-continuous.*

Proof. Obvious. \square

Remark 3.3. *The converse of the above theorem need not be true as shown in the following example.*

Example 3.6. *Consider the semi prime ideal space $X = \{a, b, c\}$,*

$\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$, $S_1 = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}$,

$\sigma = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$, $S_2 = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}$. Define $f : (X, \tau, S_1) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S_2)$ by $f(a) = a, f(b) = b, f(c) = c$. Then f is S -continuous but not strongly S -continuous.

Theorem 3.4. *every irresolute is S-continuous.*

Proof. Let $f : (X, \tau, S_1 \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S_2)$ be S -irresolute and U be open in Y . Since every open is S -open, U is open. Since f is S -irresolute, $f^{-1}(U)$ is S -open in X and hence f is S -continuous. \square

Remark 3.4. *The converse of the above theorem need not be true as shown in the following example.*

Example 3.7. *Consider the semi prime ideal space $X = \{a, b, c\}$,*

$\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$, $S_1 = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}$,

$\sigma = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$, $S_2 = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}$. Define $f : (X, \tau, S_1) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S_2)$ by $f(a) = a, f(b) = b, f(c) = c$. Then f is S -continuous but not S -irresolute.

Theorem 3.5. *Every strongly S-continuous is S-irresolute.*

Proof. Let $f : (X, \tau, S_1 \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S_2$ be strongly S-continuous and U be S-open in Y. Since f is strongly S-continuous, $f^{-1}(U)$ is open in X. Since every open is S-open, $f^{-1}(U)$ is S-open in X and hence f is irresolute. \square

Remark 3.5. *The converse of the above theorem need not be true as shown in the following example.*

Example 3.8. *Consider the semi prime ideal space $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$, $S_1 = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}$, $\sigma = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$, $S_2 = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \tau, S_1) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S_2)$ by $f(a) = a, f(b) = c, f(c) = b$. Then f is S-irresolute but not strongly S-continuous.*

Example 3.9. *The concepts continuous and S-irresolute are independent to each other. For, consider the semi prime ideal space $X = \{a, b, c\}$,*

$\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$, $S_1 = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}$, $\sigma = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$, $S_2 = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \tau, S_1) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S_2)$ by $f(a) = a, f(b) = b, f(c) = c$. Then f is not S-irresolute but continuous.

Consider the semi prime ideal space $X = \{a, b, c\}, \tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$, $S_1 = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}, \sigma = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$, $S_2 = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \tau, S_1) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S_2)$ by $f(a) = a, f(b) = c, f(c) = b$. Then f is S-irresolute but not continuous.

Theorem 3.6. *Let $f : (X, \tau, S_1) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S_2)$ be a function. Then*

1. *f is S-continuous iff inverse image of every closed in Y is S-closed in X.*
2. *f is S-irresolute iff inverse image of every S-closed set in Y is S-closed in X.*
3. *f is strongly S-continuous iff inverse image of every S-closed in Y is closed in X*

Proof. Obvious \square

Theorem 3.7. *Let X and Y be topological spaces and $f : X \rightarrow Y$. Then f is S-continuous iff for each $x \in X$ and each neighbourhood V of f(x), there is a S-neighbourhood U of x such that $f(U) \subset V$.*

Proof. Let V be neighbourhood in f(x). Since f is S-continuous, $f^{-1}(V)$ is S-open in X. Let $U = f^{-1}(V)$. Then U is S-open and hence S-neighbourhood of x which gives $f(U) \subset V$.

Conversely assume that for each $x \in X$ and each neighbourhood V of f(x), there is a S-neighbourhood U of x such that $f(U) \subset V$. Let B be open set in Y and let $x \in f^{-1}(B)$. Then $f(x) \in B$ and hence B is a neighbourhood of f(x). By assumption, there is a S-neighbourhood A_x of x such that $f(A_x) \subset B$. Then $A_x \subset f^{-1}(B)$ for each x. This gives $f^{-1}(B) = \cup A_x$. Since every A_x is S-open, $\cup A_x$ is S-open which gives $f^{-1}(B)$ is open and hence f is S-continuous. \square

4. Contra and totally continuous in semi prime ideal space

In this section we defined contra S-continuous in semi prime ideal space and compared with continuous functions. Also we defined totally S-continuous functions and discussed.

Definition 4.1. A function $f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is said to be contra S-continuous if inverse image of every open in Y is S-closed in X.

Example 4.1. Consider the semi prime ideal space $X = \{a, b, c\}, \tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$,
 $S = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}, \sigma = \{\phi, \{b\}, X\}$. Define
 $f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ by $f(a) = b, f(b) = c, f(c) = a$. Then f is contra S -continuous.

Definition 4.2. A function $f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is said to be totally S -continuous if inverse image of every open is S -clopen in X .

Example 4.2. Consider the semi prime ideal space $X = \{a, b, c\}, \tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$,
 $S = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}, \sigma = \{\phi, \{b\}, X\}$. Define
 $f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ by $f(a) = b, f(b) = c, f(c) = a$. Then f is totally S -continuous.

Theorem 4.1. Every totally S -continuous is contra S -continuous.

Proof. Let $f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be totally S -continuous and U be open set in Y . Since f is totally S -continuous $f^{-1}(U)$ is S -clopen in X . Therefore $f^{-1}(U)$ is S -closed and hence f is contra S -continuous. \square

Example 4.3. The converse of above theorem is not always true. For Consider the semi prime ideal space
 $X = \{a, b, c\}, \tau = \{\phi, \{b, c\}, X\}$,
 $S = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}, \sigma = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$. Define
 $f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ by $f(a) = a, f(b) = b, f(c) = c$. Then f is contra S -continuous but not totally S -continuous.

Theorem 4.2. Every contra continuous is contra S -continuous.

Proof. Let $f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be contra continuous and U be open set in Y . Since f is contra continuous $f^{-1}(U)$ is S -closed in X . Since every closed is S -closed, $f^{-1}(U)$ is S -closed in X and hence f is contra S -continuous. \square

Example 4.4. The converse of above theorem is not always true. For Consider the semi prime ideal space
 $X = \{a, b, c\}, \tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$,
 $S = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}, \sigma = \{\phi, \{b\}, X\}$. Define
 $f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ by $f(a) = b, f(b) = c, f(c) = a$. Then f is contra S -continuous but not contra continuous.

Theorem 4.3. Every totally continuous is totally S -continuous.

Proof. Let $f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be totally continuous and U be open set in Y . Since f is totally continuous $f^{-1}(U)$ is clopen in X . Since every clopen is S -clopen, $f^{-1}(U)$ is S -clopen in X and hence f is totally S -continuous. \square

Example 4.5. The converse of above theorem need not be always true. For Consider the semi prime ideal space
 $X = \{a, b, c\}, \tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$,
 $S = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}, \sigma = \{\phi, \{b\}, X\}$. Define
 $f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ by $f(a) = b, f(b) = c, f(c) = a$. Then f is totally S -continuous but not totally continuous.

Theorem 4.4. every totally continuous is contra S -continuous.

Proof. Obvious. \square

Example 4.6. *The converse of above theorem need not be always true.*

For consider the semi prime ideal space $X = \{a, b, c\}, \tau = \{\phi, \{b, c\}, X\}$,

$S = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}, \sigma = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$. Define

$f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ by $f(a) = a, f(b) = b, f(c) = c$. Then f is contra S -continuous but not totally continuous.

Theorem 4.5. *Every totally S -continuous is S -continuous.*

Proof. Let $f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be totally S -continuous and U be open set in Y . Since f is totally S -continuous, $f^{-1}(U)$ is S -clopen in X and hence S -open in X . Therefore f is S -continuous. □

Example 4.7. *The converse of above theorem need not be always true.*

For consider the semi prime ideal space $X = \{a, b, c\}, \tau = \{\phi, \{b, c\}, X\}$,

$S = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}, \sigma = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$. Define

$f : (X, \tau, S) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ by $f(a) = a, f(b) = b, f(c) = c$. Then f is S -continuous but not totally S -continuous.

5. composition of functions in semi prime ideal space

In this section we discussed about the composition of continuous functions in semi prime ideal space.

Theorem 5.1. *Let $f : (X, \tau, S_1) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S_2)$ and $g : (Y, \sigma, S_2) \rightarrow (Z, \delta, S_3)$ be bijection mappings. If*

1. *f is strongly S -continuous and g is strongly S -continuous, then $g \circ f$ is strongly S -continuous.*
2. *f is strongly S -continuous and g is strongly S -continuous, then $g \circ f$ is continuous.*
3. *f is strongly S -continuous and g is strongly S -continuous, then $g \circ f$ is S -continuous.*
4. *f is strongly S -continuous and g is strongly S -continuous, then $g \circ f$ is S -irresolute.*

Proof.

1. Let V be S -open in Z . Since g is strongly S -continuous, $g^{-1}(V)$ is open in Y and hence $g^{-1}(V)$ is S -open in Y . Since f is strongly S -continuous, $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V))$ is open in X . Since f and g are bijections, $(g \circ f)^{-1}(V)$ is open in X . Therefore $g \circ f$ is strongly S -continuous.

(2),(3) and (4) are obvious. □

Theorem 5.2. *Let $f : (X, \tau, S_1) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S_2)$ and $g : (Y, \sigma, S_2) \rightarrow (Z, \delta, S_3)$ be bijection mappings. If*

1. *f is strongly S -continuous and g is S -irresolute, then $g \circ f$ is strongly S -continuous.*
2. *f is strongly S -continuous and g is S -irresolute, then $g \circ f$ is continuous.*
3. *f is strongly S -continuous and g is S -irresolute, then $g \circ f$ is S -continuous.*
4. *f is strongly S -continuous and g is S -irresolute, then $g \circ f$ is S -irresolute.*

Proof.

1. Let V be S -open in Z . Since g is S -irresolute, $g^{-1}(V)$ is S -open in Y . Since f is strongly S -continuous, $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V))$ is open in X . Since f and g are bijections, $(g \circ f)^{-1}(V)$ is open in X . Therefore $g \circ f$ is strongly S -continuous.

(2),(3) and (4) are obvious. □

Theorem 5.3. *Let $f : (X, \tau, S_1) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S_2)$ and $g : (Y, \sigma, S_2) \rightarrow (Z, \delta, S_3)$ be bijection mappings. If*

1. *f is strongly S -continuous and g is S -continuous, then $g \circ f$ is continuous.*
2. *f is strongly S -continuous and g is S -continuous, then $g \circ f$ is S -continuous.*
3. *f is strongly S -continuous and g is continuous, then $g \circ f$ is continuous.*
4. *f is strongly S -continuous and g is continuous, then $g \circ f$ is S -continuous.*

Proof.

1. Let V be open in Z . Since g is S -continuous, $g^{-1}(V)$ is S -open in Y . Since f is strongly S -continuous, $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V))$ is open in X . Since f and g are bijections, $(g \circ f)^{-1}(V)$ is open in X . Therefore $g \circ f$ is continuous.

(2),(3) and (4) are obvious. □

Theorem 5.4. *Let $f : (X, \tau, S_1) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S_2)$ and $g : (Y, \sigma, S_2) \rightarrow (Z, \delta, S_3)$ be bijection mappings. If*

1. *f is S -irresolute and g is S -continuous, then $g \circ f$ is continuous.*
2. *f is strongly S -continuous and g is S -irresolute, then $g \circ f$ is S -irresolute.*
3. *f is S -irresolute and g is strongly S -continuous, then $g \circ f$ is S -irresolute.*
4. *f is S -irresolute and g is strongly S -continuous, then $g \circ f$ is S -continuous.*
5. *f is S -irresolute and g is S -continuous, then $g \circ f$ is S -continuous.*
6. *f is S -irresolute and g is continuous, then $g \circ f$ is S -continuous.*

Proof. (1) Let V be S -open in Z . Since g is S -irresolute, $g^{-1}(V)$ is S -open in Y . Since f is S -irresolute, $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V))$ is S -open in X . Since f and g are bijections, $(g \circ f)^{-1}(V)$ is S -open in X . Therefore $g \circ f$ is S -irresolute.

(2),(3) and (4) are obvious.

(5) Let V be S -open in Z . Since g is S -continuous, $g^{-1}(V)$ is S -open in Y . Since f is S -irresolute, $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V))$ is S -open in X . Since f and g are bijections, $(g \circ f)^{-1}(V)$ is S -open in X . Therefore $g \circ f$ is S -continuous.

(6) obvious. □

Theorem 5.5. *Let $f : (X, \tau, S_1) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S_2)$ and $g : (Y, \sigma, S_2) \rightarrow (Z, \delta, S_3)$ be bijection mappings. If*

1. *f is S -continuous and g is strongly S -continuous, then $g \circ f$ is S -irresolute.*
2. *f is S -continuous and g is strongly S -continuous, then $g \circ f$ is S -continuous.*
3. *f is S -continuous and g is continuous, then $g \circ f$ is S -continuous.*

Proof. (1) Let V be S -open in Z . Since g is strongly S -continuous, $g^{-1}(V)$ is open in Y . Since f is S -continuous, $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V))$ is S -open in X . Since f and g are bijections, $(g \circ f)^{-1}(V)$ is S -open in X . Therefore $g \circ f$ is S -irresolute.

(2) Obvious.

(3) Let V be open in Z . Since g is continuous, $g^{-1}(V)$ is open in Y . Since f is S -continuous, $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V))$ is S -open in X . Since f and g are bijections, $(g \circ f)^{-1}(V)$ is S -open in X . Therefore $g \circ f$ is S -continuous. □

Theorem 5.6. *Let $f : (X, \tau, S_1) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, S_2)$ and $g : (Y, \sigma, S_2) \rightarrow (Z, \delta, S_3)$ be bijection mappings. If*

1. *f is continuous and g is strongly continuous, then $g \circ f$ is S -continuous.*
2. *f is continuous and g is strongly S -continuous, then $g \circ f$ is strongly S -continuous.*
3. *f is S -continuous and g is strongly S -continuous, then $g \circ f$ is S -irresolute.*

Proof.

1. Let V be open in Z . Since g is continuous, $g^{-1}(V)$ is open in Y . Since f is continuous $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V))$ is open in X . Since f and g are bijections, $(g \circ f)^{-1}(V)$ is open in X and hence $(g \circ f)^{-1}(V)$ is S -open in X . Therefore $g \circ f$ is S -continuous.
2. Let V be S -open in Z . Since g is strongly S -continuous, $g^{-1}(V)$ is open in Y . Since f is continuous $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V))$ is open in X . Since f and g are bijections, $(g \circ f)^{-1}(V)$ is open in X . Therefore $g \circ f$ is strongly S -continuous.
3. obvious.

□

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